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**Teachers the Backbone of Indian Economy -
A Study of Teachers Stress With Reference To Aided, Unaided, and Public Schools**

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Abstract

The worker's response to work stress can be either psychological, physical or both and is usually categorized as being acute, post traumatic, or chronic. National surveys in the United Kingdom , Australia and India have reported a serious and growing problem of academic work stress with several deleterious consequences including decreased job satisfaction, reduced morale and ill health for academic staff. The outcome of stress may be of: emotional manifestations , dissatisfaction, depression, feelings of undefined anxiety, fear and low self-esteem with a possible extreme result being burnout; behavioral manifestations - behavioral issues such as hungry disorders, excessive smoking and alcohol or drug abuse, violence , sleep disorders , possible displays of withdrawal symptoms that is absence and resignations from the profession.

Key words: Work stress, Labour welfare, stress management, Teacher stress, and emotional intelligence.

Introduction

Role stress may be viewed as the consequence of disparity between an individual's perception of the characteristics of a specific role and what is actually being achieved by the individual currently performing the specific role. Thus, role stress occurs when there is difference between perceived role expectations and achievement. Burnout is defined as a syndrome of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment, and found that burnout is strongly related to work overload, a lack of social support and role stress.

Review of Literature

Tasleema et al.(2013), The measurement of social and family role stress among primary school teachers. The Social and Family Role Stress Scale (SFRS) by S. Sultan

Akhter and Priti Vadra were administered. The analysis of the data showed that Female primary school teachers were found to have more stress as compared to male primary school teachers of District Budgam.

Durban (2013) examined the different sources of stress among elementary school teachers in Metro Manila. The samples were randomly chosen among elementary school teachers. The study reports that of the four sources of stress identified, the Pupils' behaviour and achievement recorded a significant difference among the variables identified. Results indicate that of the different sources of stress students' behaviour was considered as having the most significant influence among teachers.

Martin (2009) defined stress as unpleasant state of emotional and physiological arousal that people experience in situations that they perceive as dangerous or threatening to their well-being. The word stress means different things to different people. Stress is defined as events or situations that cause them to feel tension, pressure, or negative emotions such as anxiety and anger. Others view stress as the response to these situations. This response includes physiological changes—such as increased heart rate and muscle tension—as well as emotional and behavioral changes. However, most psychologists regard stress as a process involving a person's interpretation and response to a threatening event.

Methodology

About 390 public and private (35 per cent males and 65 per cent females) are taken for the study. The teachers' age ranged from <25 to >45 years (49 per cent aged between 31 to 35). The majority of teachers were married and the majority of the sample had been teaching from 1 to 10 years as per the formula the estimated sample size required is 376 the final the sample size is 390. Job Stress outcomes - Teacher Stress Inventory (Schutz & Long, 1988)

Table 1: Number of schools Taken for the study.

Type of school	Available	Percentage in total	Required Sample size
Public	7,942	45.6 %	178
Private Aided	2,811	16.2%	63
Private Unaided	6,640	38.2%	149
Total	17,393	100%	390

Source: Primary Data

The Teacher Stress Inventory (revised by Schutz & Long, 1988) identified what types of situations teachers reported as being stressful and an overall stress score. The shortened version has 36 items that are rated on a 5-point Likert scale. These items are grouped into seven categories which include: role ambiguity; role stress ; organizational management ; job satisfaction ; life satisfaction ; task stress and supervisory support .A high score indicates a higher degree of stress experienced by the participant. A high score on one scale indicates that the participant has a high amount of stress in that area. The maximum score is 180.

Result and Discussion

Segmentation of Teachers Job Stress

This procedure attempts to identify relatively homogeneous groups of cases based on the selected characteristics, using an algorithm that can handle large numbers of cases. The Teachers Job Stress can be classified into three categories based on Stress level they have on Supervisory Support, Role ambiguity, Role Stress, Organizational management, Jobs Satisfaction, Life Satisfaction and Task Stress. The Teachers Job Stress is classified into three segments because the difference among the coefficients is significant only on three cases on the hierarchical cluster. For the purpose of classification of investors K-Means cluster is used.

Table 2 : Final Cluster Centers

Stress level	Cluster					
	1	Rank	2	Rank	3	Rank
Supervisory Support	4.03	I	3.18	II	2.53	III
Role ambiguity	4.41	I	3.50	II	2.37	III
Role Stress	4.01	II	4.39	I	2.99	III
Organizational management	3.95	I	3.91	II	2.57	III
Jobs Satisfaction	4.32	I	3.32	II	3.05	III
Life Satisfaction	4.23	I	3.11	II	2.57	III
Task Stress	4.06	I	2.61	II	2.49	III
Average	4.14		3.43		2.65	

The Final Cluster Centers table shows the mean values of all the Teachers Job Stress factors are in the three final clusters. The mean values of Teachers Job Stress in the final clusters centers table reflect the attributes of each cluster. It is also noted from the table that

no particular stress factors is heavily loaded on any particular cluster segment. Table 2 portrays that the Teachers Job Stress can be divided into three distinct clusters based on their response. These clusters may be designated as "High level of stress", "Medium level of stress" and "Low level of stress". The rank of the clusters on Teachers Job Stress is also given in the above table. The description of the characteristics of all the three clusters or segments along with the label is given below.

Table 3 : ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	Df		
Supervisory Support	75.52	2	0.18	387	417.41	0.00
Role ambiguity	143.78	2	0.13	387	1.04E3	0.00
Role Stress	74.32	2	0.21	387	353.78	0.00
Organizational management	88.84	2	0.13	387	653.63	0.00
Jobs Satisfaction	56.28	2	0.24	387	226.24	0.00
Life Satisfaction	92.45	2	0.17	387	540.45	0.00
Task Stress	92.33	2	0.21	387	423.51	0.00

The final cluster centers table shows that the three clusters differ in mean value of all the seven criteria. But the ANOVA table indicates that the difference exists among the three clusters in the mean values of seven aspects of stress level factors are significant. The significant value for all stress level factor is 0.00. This indicates that the mean values of all the seven perceptions are significantly different among three clusters. This also means that all the seven stress factors are influencing significantly in dividing people into three segments based on stress levels.

Table 4 : Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	110.00	28.20%
	2	107.00	27.44%
	3	173.00	44.36%
Valid		390.00	

The Number of cases in each cluster table indicates that around 110 Teachers out of 390 Teachers are in cluster I which is the High level of stress group and 107 out of 390 Teachers are in Medium level of stress group. This means that around 28.20 percent of Teachers are in High level of stress segment and 27.44 percent of Teachers are in Medium level of stress group. In cluster three 44.36 percent of the Teachers are comes under Low level of stress group.

Table 5 : Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and income

Stress level	Income			Total	Value	Sig. Value
	15001 - 20000	20001- 25000	>25000			
High	9	17	84	110	10.02	0.04
Medium	9	9	89	107		
Low	17	8	148	173		
Total	35	34	321	390		

H₀: There is no association between level of stress and Income

The association between the level of stress and the income of respondents has been find out by chi-square tests. From the table there are 35 respondents got 150001-20000 as their monthly salary, out of them 17 respondents got low level of stress and 9 of them having high level of stress. There are 321 respondents got more than 25000 as their salary, out of them 84 having high level of stress, and 148 of them low level of stress. The results inferred that the lower the income of the respondents lead to high level of stress that is more than 50 percent of the respondents in the income group 150001 to 20000 having high level of stress, Chi-square value in this research is 10.02, and the p-value is 0.04 so it is inferred that there is statistical significant association between the level of stress and income of the respondents, so the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Independent variables considered in the study, such as age, community, marital status, educational qualification, nature of the subjects the teachers teaching, salary received by the teachers and location of the school are significantly predicting the occupational stress of higher secondary teachers. The studies from Mariya (2012) shows there is no significant difference between monthly salary and occupational stress among school teachers. Teachers with higher monthly income are not necessarily having higher stress levels than their colleagues with lower monthly income, vice versa.

Figure 1 : Associations between Income and Teachers Job Stress

Figure 1 portrays the results of Correspondence Analysis to explore the association between the income and teachers job stress. The Figure 4.07 displays that teachers income falls between 15001 to 20000 are closely associated with “Low level of stress group”, while teachers income greater than 25000 are closely associated “Medium level of stress” group. Teacher’s income between 20001 to 25000 is closely associated with the “High level of stress”.

Table 6: Chi- Square test result to find out the association between level of stress and Practicing Specific Activities

Stress Level	Practicing Specific Activities						Total	Value	Sig. Value
	Yoga	meditation	music	sports	religious activities	nothing			
High	10	17	0	9	20	54	110	219.50	0.00
Medium	9	9	19	9	52	9	107		
Low	17	80	42	17	17	0	173		
Total	36	106	61	35	89	63	390		

H_0 : There is no association between level of stress and Specific Activity Practiced

Chi-square test is used to find out the association between the level of stress and specific activity practicing. From the results it is inferred that there are 36 respondents who

are practicing yoga out of them 10 are having high level of stress, 17 of them avail with low level of stress. 106 respondents doing meditation out of them 17 are having high level of stress, 80 of them having low level of stress, 61 respondents having interest in music out of them 42 of them having low level of stress and none of them inferred with high level of stress. There are 35 respondents practicing sports activity and out of that 9 of them having high level of stress and 9 of them having medium level of stress and 17 of them having low level of stress. There are 89 respondents coped with religious activity out of them 20 of them having high level of stress, 17 of them having low level of stress, there are 63 respondents not interest in any activities to relieve stress out of that 63, 54 of them having high level of stress, 9 of them having medium level of stress, no one is inferred with low level of stress. The chi-square value for this table is 219.50 with respective 0.00 p-value it is inferred that there is a statistical significant association between the level of stress and practicing specific activities. The study by Anderson (1999) employed a pretest-posttest control group design and used the Teacher's Stress Inventory (TSI), State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), and the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) to assess the effect of a 5-week standardized meditation (SM) class on the perceived occupational stress of 91 full-time teachers from seven suburban school districts in three states. Results were consistent with the hypothesis that SM significantly reduces teachers' perceived stress. Teachers perceived a reduction in stress using SM only 2-5 times per week. The use of standardized meditation by school psychologists to assist in reducing teacher stress.

Figure 2 : Associations between Practice of Specific Activities and Teachers Job Stress

Figure portrays the results of Correspondence Analysis to explore the association between practicing of specific activities teachers' job stress. The Figure 2 displays that teachers those who are practicing and having interest in music and meditation are closely associated with "Low level of stress group", while teachers following religious activities are closely associated "Medium level of stress" group. Teachers those who are not practicing any activities are closely associated with the "High level of stress"

Table 7 : Analysis of variance results for Monthly Income and Teacher Stress

Job Dimensions	Stress	Monthly Income/Rupees	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	F	Sig. Value
Supervisory Support		15001 - 20000	35	16.88	4.83	0.81	9.66	0.00
		20001- 25000	34	21.50	5.23	0.89		
		> 25000	321	18.71	4.28	0.23		
		Total	390	18.79	4.52	0.22		
Role Ambiguity		15001 - 20000	35	5.57	2.63	0.44	6.12	0.00
		20001- 25000	34	7.05	1.87	0.32		
		> 25000	321	6.55	1.74	0.09		
		Total	390	6.51	1.87	0.09		
Role Stress		15001 - 20000	35	15.37	4.32	0.73	14.50	0.00
		20001- 25000	34	19.97	3.19	0.54		
		> 25000	321	18.43	3.69	0.20		
		Total	390	18.29	3.84	0.19		
Organisational Management		15001 - 20000	35	15.14	5.27	0.89	11.45	0.00
		20001- 25000	34	19.29	2.40	0.41		
		> 25000	321	16.52	3.66	0.20		
		Total	390	16.64	3.84	0.19		
Job Satisfaction		15001 - 20000	35	16.85	3.82	0.64	10.06	0.00
		20001- 25000	34	20.02	0.71	0.12		
		> 25000	321	17.19	3.72	0.20		
		Total	390	17.41	3.66	0.18		

Life Satisfaction	15001 - 20000	35	15.11	4.12	0.69	8.42	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	18.52	2.27	0.38		
	> 25000	321	15.76	4.05	0.22		
	Total	390	15.94	4.01	0.20		
Task Stress	15001 - 20000	35	14.57	2.92	0.49	5.20	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	17.00	3.15	0.54		
	> 25000	321	14.62	4.30	0.24		
	Total	390	14.82	4.15	0.21		

One way ANOVA is carried out to test the influence of respondents income with the respective to job stress , the mean value denotes that the middle category that is the respondents having 20,001- 25,000 rupees salary (per month) has the high level of teachers stress in the present study for all the seven dimensions in the teachers stress variable. The F-value and p-value denotes that there are opinion differences with respondent's salary with the teachers stress dimensions Role Ambiguity, Role Stress, Organisational Management, Job Satisfaction, Life Satisfaction and Task Stress. In a study in Bahrain Al-Khalefa (1999) found the major causes of stress for physical education teachers to be: salaries, bonuses and allowances; work conditions; status of physical education; supervision; school facilities; workload; career development.

Table 8 : Multivariate analysis of variance test results for Teachers stress dimensions with type of school Vs. designation

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of school	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value
Supervisory Support	Public	Secondary Grade	16.81	2.56	160	18.56	0.00
		B.T	23.33	6.20	18		
		Total	17.47	3.67	178		
	Private Aided	Secondary Grade	19.83	6.97	42		
		B.T	25.14	5.09	21		
		Total	21.60	6.84	63		
	Private	Secondary Grade	18.99	3.55	113		

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of school	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value	
Role Ambiguity	Un-aided	B.T	19.75	3.39	36	52.16	0.00	
		Total	19.17	3.52	149			
		Secondary Grade	18.00	3.96	315			
			B.T	22.12	5.19			75
				Total	18.79			4.52
		Public	Secondary Grade	5.81	1.53			160
	B.T		7.27	2.13	18			
	Total		5.96	1.66	178			
	Private Aided	Secondary Grade	6.50	2.83	42			
		B.T	7.71	1.61	21			
Total		6.90	2.54	63				
Private Un-aided	Secondary Grade	7.00	1.63	113				
	B.T	7.00	1.43	36				
	Total	7.00	1.58	149				
Total	Secondary Grade	6.33	1.87	315				
	B.T	7.26	1.67	75				
	Total	6.51	1.87	390				
Role Stress	Public	Secondary Grade	17.63	4.93	160	17.82	4.78	
		B.T	19.44	2.70	18			
		Total	17.82	4.78	178			
	Private Aided	Secondary Grade	16.47	4.88	42			
		B.T	20.85	3.02	21			
		Total	17.93	4.80	63			
	Private Un-aided	Secondary Grade	18.93	1.04	113			
		B.T	19.25	0.84	36			
		Total	19.01	1.00	149			

Job Dimensions	Stress Type of school	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value
Organisational Management	Total	Secondary Grade	17.94	4.06	315		
		B.T	19.74	2.23	75		
		Total	18.29	3.84	390		
	Public	Secondary Grade	14.49	2.82	160		
		B.T	19.38	2.19	18		
		Total	14.98	3.13	178		
	Private Aided	Secondary Grade	16.47	5.46	42		
		B.T	20.00	1.73	21		
		Total	17.65	4.84	63		
Private Un-aided	Secondary Grade	17.94	3.30	113			
	B.T	19.00	3.36	36			
	Total	18.20	3.33	149			
Total	Secondary Grade	15.99	3.79	315			
	B.T	19.37	2.73	75			
	Total	16.64	3.84	390			
Job Satisfaction	Public	Secondary Grade	14.35	2.67	160		
		B.T	19.72	0.46	18		
		Total	14.89	3.01	178		
	Private Aided	Secondary Grade	18.95	5.51	42		
		B.T	19.85	0.35	21		
		Total	19.25	4.51	63		
	Private Un-aided	Secondary Grade	19.61	1.39	113		
		B.T	19.75	1.10	36		
		Total	19.65	1.33	149		
	Total	Secondary Grade	16.85	3.85	315		
		B.T	19.77	0.81	75		

Job Dimensions	Stress	Type of school	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value	
Life Satisfaction			Total	17.41	3.66	390			
	Public	Secondary Grade	Secondary Grade	13.18	2.99	160			
			B.T	19.77	3.15	18			
			Total	13.84	3.60	178			
		Private Aided	Secondary Grade	17.50	5.56	42			
			B.T	20.71	2.55	21			
			Total	18.57	4.99	63			
	Private Un-aided	Secondary Grade	17.29	2.59	113				
		B.T	17.50	2.21	36				
		Total	17.34	2.49	149				
	Total	Secondary Grade	15.23	3.91	315				
		B.T	18.94	2.90	75				
		Total	15.94	4.01	390				
	Task Stress	Public	Secondary Grade	Secondary Grade	12.07	3.69	160		
				B.T	18.00	3.30	18		
Total				12.67	4.06	178			
Private Aided			Secondary Grade	17.88	5.20	42			
			B.T	19.28	2.77	21			
			Total	18.34	4.56	63			
Private Un-aided		Secondary Grade	15.95	2.29	113				
		B.T	15.750	1.94	36				
		Total	15.90	2.21	149				
Total		Secondary Grade	14.24	4.19	315				
		B.T	17.28	2.96	75				
		Total	14.82	4.15	390				

To find out the relationship between type of school and designation of the respondents with the teachers stress multivariate analysis is carried out. From the mean value it is inferred that for most of the dimensions of teacher stress dimensions the highest mean value is obtained by Bachelors teaching assistant (B.T) category especially from Private aided school teachers, which it denotes that the B.T teachers who belongs to Private-aided school having more stress than Secondary grade teachers from public and private –un aided school teachers. The F-Value for the type of school, designation and type of school Vs. Designation is found to be 18.56, 52.16 and 18.23 and its corresponding p-value 0.00, 0.00 and 0.00 it confirms the same. Hence respondents differ in their opinion regarding stress based on both type of school, designation individually and collectively. The study by Manju (2012) points out the need to establish self-regulatory model for private schools as they have to follow regulations, with regard to number of class rooms, teacher salaries, their qualifications, playground size, school facilities, library, laboratories, and so on. Care need to be taken that these regulations should be both for government as well as for private schools. For universalizing schooling government and private sector need to develop in such a way that both could play a supportive role in education. Besides steps need to be taken to improve government schools also, so that healthy and reasonable competition between government and private schools could be in place to benefit all the children.

Table 9 : Relationship between Teachers Stress and dimensions of Organisational Climate

Organisational Climate	Supportive Behaviour	Directive Behaviour	Engaged Behaviour	Frustrated Behaviour	Intimate Behaviour
Directive Behaviour	.701*				
Engaged Behaviour	.744*	.961*			
Frustrated Behaviour	.728*	.469*	.476*		
Intimate Behaviour	.491*	.689*	.673*	.512*	
Teachers Stress	.509*	.283*	.311*	.807*	.487*

While testing about the correlations between teacher stress and organisational climate dimension teachers frustrated behaviour has the highest percentage of influence i.e. 80.7 percent over the teachers stress. And the Frustrated Behaviour has the positive and significance relationship with teacher stress. The incidence of stress and burnout are usually high for human service professionals, including teachers. Stress describes negative feelings resulting from work that may include anger, frustration, tension and/or depression that threaten a professional's sense of well-being (Howard et al 2004). There are variations in the results; the lowest relationship with teacher stress is 0.283 Directive behaviour of principal behaviour. The next highest influence over the teacher stress to directive behaviour is engaged behaviour of teachers in the school. There are some similarities between the influence of supportive behaviour of principle and intimate behaviour of teachers in effect to teachers stress.

Findings

- Private un-aided school has highest influence for the teacher stress dimensions role ambiguity, role stress, organisational management and job satisfaction, all seven teacher stress dimensions has the significance and opinions differ regarding the type of school.
- Secondary grade teachers have highest influence over the teacher stress dimensions than the Bachelors Teachers (B.T).
- For all the seven dimension of teacher stress respondents have has significant differences in their opinion based on the designation of respondents.
- Significant difference in the opinion among the respondents based on their designation with all the seven dimensions of teachers stress.
- The respondents who got 20,000 to 25,000 as salary have highest influence on job stress than any other category.
- All the seven dimensions of teachers job stress have significant difference based on the income of the respondents.
- The respondents who are having 3 to 5 teaching hours have the highest influence with the teacher stress. Except the teacher stress dimension task stress all other six dimension has the statistical significant for the teacher stress.
- Respondents differ in their opinion regarding stress based on both the type of school, designation as individually and collectively.
- For the dimension role ambiguity the public and private aided school teachers who have high monthly income have more mean value.

- The respondent's opinion differs positively and statistically significant with respect to the type of school and income individually and collectively.
- The correlations between teacher stress and organisational climate dimensions teachers frustrated behaviour has the highest percentage of influence.
- The dimensions of teacher's effectiveness interpersonal relation have high correlation with coping strategies than the dimensions teaching ability, teaching competence, personality and evaluation.
- The factors of organisational climate dimensions teacher's behaviour, frustrated behaviour and intimate behaviour are found to have positive as well as correlated with coping strategies, the teacher's behaviour dimension engaged behaviour does not significant with coping strategies practiced by respondents.

Conclusion

The progress of the country depends upon the quality of teachers, building, equipment, instructional material, up-to-date library, well developed curriculum etc. These all are necessary but, without qualified and highly motivated teachers, these are of no value. Teacher is considered as a core stone of successful education system. A number of external and internal factors acts upon a teacher and influences his/her behavior in implementing the education policy of nation. So there is need to identify these factors which influence the teacher. The teacher plays an important role in shaping the behavior of student especially in beginning years. A teacher who is satisfied with his job can perform his duties efficiently and effectively and has a positive attitude towards teaching, but if the teacher is in under stress then the teacher cannot work effectively and has a negative attitude towards his job.

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